

Repurposing Therapeutics: Strategies for Drug Development, Challenges and Applications

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Abstract: In recent years, the world has seen an unprecedented rise in disease outbreaks, while the pace of new drug discoveries remains slow and costly, taking up to 15 years and \$2-3 billion per drug, with a success rate of only 10%. The growing disparity has fueled interest in alternative methods, with drug repurposing gaining recognition as a viable strategy. Drug repurposing, also referred to as drug repositioning or therapeutic switching, focuses on discovering new medical applications for already known drugs, including those that are approved, failed, withdrawn, or have significant side effects. The advantages include reduced costs, shorter development timelines, and increased success ratio. Driven by advances in genomics, bioinformatics, and cheminformatics, repurposing allows drug candidates to skip early-phase trials, moving directly to later-stage clinical testing. The present review highlights the various strategies, approaches employed, each with distinct applications and limitations. The review further highlights the challenges for drug repurposing, including regulatory constraints, intellectual property limitations, and weak patent protection, which can hinder commercial investment. Nevertheless, drug repurposing has proven invaluable, particularly during global health crises such as COVID-19, where expedited development was critical.

Keywords: Drug repurposing, clinical trials, strategies, bioinformatics, cheminformatics.

1. Introduction: In the modern world human are encountering with different new diseases. The rate of new disease outbreaks far exceeds the pace of new drug discoveries, making the conventional drug development process, which spans 13-15 years and an investment of \$2 to \$3 billion [1]. Though the companies spend so much of cost the success rate of the drug entry into the market after all the regulatory approval is only 10 % [2]. Traditional drug discovery is elaborate, tedious, pricey and hazardous process [3]. Hence there is a need to meet this demand to discover the need drug by some other modern methods of drug discovery. One among them being drug repositioning, it is to discover an alternative pharmacological use of already existing drug. Drug repurposing is also known as drug

repositioning, drug rescuing, drug recycling, drug redirection and therapeutic switching [4, 5]. Drug repurposing is cost effective and reduces the time for discovering the new drug for a new disease. The source from where we can get a drug for new pharmacological indication could be already existing drug which is used for other disease. Withdrawn, banned, failed drugs, investigational drugs and enhancing the side effects of existing drugs [6-9]. Drug repurposing started way back in 1990's as an alternative to traditional drug discovery methods. Drug repurposing has gained significant attention during pandemic situations like covid-19 and Ebola's outbreak where one cannot wait for 12-15 years to discover a drug by following conventional drug discovery process [10, 11]. With the evolution in genomics, bioinformatics, cheminformatic tools and establishment of drug libraries has further enhanced the modern drug discovery process [12-15]. Repositioning if the drugs is possible as there are few diseases which share a common biological target and there are drugs which could be pleuritic [16]. The main advantages of drug repurposing strategy is least information is known for these drugs in terms of risk evaluation, clinical use and manufacturing process, it is possible to skip preclinical development and phase-I clinical trials, directly enter phase-II clinical trials [17], faster drug development [18], reduced investment [19, 20], reduced risk of investment [21], higher rate of success for repurposed drugs and are 25% and 65 % from phase-II and phase-III respectively [22, 23].

- 2. Strategies for drug repurposing:** It (Fig. 1) includes On-Target approach and Off-Target approach [24]. On-Target approach involves targeting the available drugs to the newly identifies disease targets and understanding the capability of the drug to bind with the target. Off-Target approach involves targeting the known and unknown adverse effects of the drugs and to repurpose the drug as an On-Target effect for a different use.

Fig. 1: Strategies for drug repositioning.

- 3. Approaches for drug repurposing:** There are various approaches for drug repurposing. Approach-I (Fig. 2) is based on experimental or activity-based method and *In-silico* based method. Experimental methods include both *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* methods [25]. Approach -II

(Fig. 3) is based on drug, disease and treatment-based methods [26]. Based on the structural characteristics, biological activities and the based on the adverse effects the drugs are repurposed. By thoroughly understanding the disease conditions by using various approaches such as virtual screening and molecular docking the drugs are repurposed. Based the omics data and the treatment protocols also the drugs are repurposed. Approach-III (Fig. 4) is based on the regulatory concerns the drug repurposing can be done.

Fig.2: Approach-I experimental and *in-silico* based.

Fig.3: Approach-II drug, disease and treatment based.

Fig.4: Approach-III regulatory concerns based.

- 4. Methods of drug repurposing:** There are various methods (Fig. 5) such as blinded screening, target based, knowledge based, signature based, pathway or network based and target mechanism-based methods. Blinded search or screening method is used in screening the drugs that are approved by regulatory authorities and for the drugs whose mechanism of action is not known as no information about the biologics is known. The main advantage of this method is there are high chances of employment to multiple conditions. Target based method where vast knowledge regarding the target and 3D structures of protein, drugs, disease, adverse effects etc is needed. It involves *in-vitro* HTS, *in-vivo* HTS and *in-silico* screening of the drugs from the drug libraries, docking and ligand-based screening methods are used. There are more possibilities of drug discovery by this method as the targets are directly linked to the disease mechanisms. Knowledge based method uses bioinformatics and cheminformatic tools. By using the blinded search and target-based method one cannot identify the new mechanism of the unknown target. Knowledge based method uses the known information to understand the unknown mechanism such as novel drug targets, new disease biomarkers and improves prediction accuracy. Signature based method uses disease data, it helps to discover unknown mechanism of the molecule and the drugs. Pathway or network-based method identifies the key targets for drug repurposing. It uses the genetic disease data, available metabolic pathways and protein interaction networks. Target mechanism-based method uses the treatment omics data. Mechanism of action of the drugs is understood. But very less information is available on target mechanism-based method. Hence difficult to obtain effective computational model [27-29].

Fig. 5: Methods of drug repurposing

5. Applications: By using various methods large number of drugs are repurposed. The various drugs their initial use and the repurpose use are mentioned the below Table 1.

Table 1: Applications of the various drugs that were repurposed.

S.NO	DRUG NAME	INITIAL USE	REPURPOSED USE	REFERENCE S
1	Alisporivir	Hepatitis c	Dry eye syndrome	30
2	Aluminium acetate	Topical astringent and antiseptic	Covid 19	31
3	Aluminium phosphate	Gastritis and ulcer	Covid 19	31
4	Amantidine	Influenza	Parkinson's disease	32
5	Ambroxol	Mucolytic agent	Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis	33
6	Amiloride	Acid sensing ion channel antagonist	Secondary progressive multiple sclerosis	34
7	Ambroxol	Mucolytic agent	Gaucher's disease	35
8	Ambroxol	Mucolytic agent	Myasthenia gravis	36
9	Amitriptyline	Depression	Refractory chronic cough	37
10	Amphotericin B	Antifungal	Visceral Leishmaniasis	32
11	Anastrozole	Ovulation induction	Breast carcinoma	38
12	Aprotinin	Prevents bleeding	Covid 19	39
13	Aripiprazole	Antipsychotic	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
14	Artesunate	Anti-infective	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40

15	Atenolol	Beta-blocker	Lung cancer/gastric cancer	41
16	Aspirin	Analgesia	Colorectal cancer	42
17	Aspirin	NSAID	Diffuse intrinsic pontine glioma (DIPG)	43
18	Atorvastatin (generic Lipitor)	Hyper-cholesterolaemia	Cavernous angioma	34
19	Atomoxetine	Depression and Parkinson disease	Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder	44
20	Auranofin	Rheumatoid arthritis	Antimicrobial	45
21	Auranofin	Anti-arthritic	Gastrointestinal stromal tumors	46
22	Avermectin B1a	Anti-infective	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
23	Azathioprine	Crohn's disease	Antimicrobial	45
24	Bacitracin	Anti-infective	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
25	Baricitinib	Antiinflammatory, Antineoplastic	2019 Cov respiratory disease	47
26	Batimastat	Metastatic cancer	Rattlesnake bites	48
27	Benzbromarone	Vasodilator	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
28	Benzbromarone	Gout	Familial amyloid polyneuropathy	49
29	Berberine	Bacterial diarrhoea	Colorectal adenoma (under phase III clinical trials)	50
30	Bithionate disodium	Anti-infective	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
31	Bleomycin	Antitumor	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40

32	Brexpiprazole	Anti-psychotic	cancer	46
33	Bromperidol	Antipsychotic/Antidepressant	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
34	Broxyquinoline	Anti-infective	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
35	Bumetanide	Edema	Skin infections	51
36	Bupivacaine	Local anaesthetic	Alzheimer's disease	52
37	Calcium channel blocker	Hypertension	Acute coronary syndrome	53
38	Canakinumab	Rheumatoid Arthritis; approved for CAPS by the FDA	Acute coronary syndrome	54
39	Capecitabine	Colon cancer	Breast carcinoma	38
40	Carboplatin	Antitumor	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
41	Carvedilol	Alpha- and Beta blockers	Glioblastoma/Breast carcinoma	41
42	Celecoxib	Anti-inflammatory/Immunomodulatory	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
43	Chloroquine	Anti-malarial	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
44	Chlorpromazine	Anti-psychotic	Glioblastoma (under phase II clinical trials)	55
45	chloroquine	Antimalarial	Pancreatic cancer	41

46	Cimetidine	Reduce stomach acid	Lung adenocarcinoma (Under pre-clinical trials)	56
47	Cisplatin	Antitumor	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
48	Clarithromycin, pioglitazone, and treosulfan	Antibiotic Antidiabetic	Non-small cell lung cancer	57
49	Clobetasol	Allergic rhinitis	Chronic myelo proliferative disorder	30
50	Clomiphene	Fertility	Antimicrobial	45
51	Colchicine	Gout	Acute coronary syndrome	58
52	Curcumin	Dermatological diseases	Prostate cancer, Colon cancer (under phase III clinical trials)	59
53	Cyclophosphamide	As immunomodulator in autoimmune diseases	Breast carcinoma	38
54	Cyclosporine	Immuno suppressant	Anti-fungal	60
55	Cyproterone acetate	Anti androgen therapy	Covid 19	31
56	Dacarbazine	Antitumor	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
57	Dapagliflozin	Type 2 Diabetes mellitus	Heart failure	61
58	Dapoxetine	Depression and Analgesia	Premature ejaculation	62
59	Daunorubicin	Acute myeloid leukemia, acute lymphocytic leukemia, chronic myelogenous leukemia, and Kaposi's sarcoma	Antimicrobial	45

60	Dexamethasone	Rheumatoid arthritis	Covid 19	31
61	Dexpramipexole	ALS and other neurological diseases: phase 3 trials did not meet the endpoint	Hyper eosinophilic syndromes	34
62	Diazepam	Antipsychotic/Antidepressant	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
63	Diclofenac	NSAID, analgesia	Basal cell carcinoma (under Phase II clinical trials)	63
64	Digoxin	Treatment for cardiac diseases	Anticancer	64
65	Dihydroartemisinin	Anti-infective	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
66	Dimethyl Fumarate	Allergies	Multiple sclerosis	32
67	Disulfiram	Reduces ethanol tolerance in alcoholism	Metastatic Breast carcinoma & Alzheimer's disease	34
68	Docetaxel	Hormone-refractory prostate cancer	Breast carcinoma and Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
69	Donepezil	Alzheimer disease	HF and coronary outcomes	65
70	Doxepin	Antipsychotic/Antidepressant	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
71	Doxorubicin	Antibiotic from Streptomyces peucetius bacterium	Bladder, breast, stomach, lung, ovarian, and thyroid cancers	38,46
72	Doxycycline	Antibacterial	Malaria	32
73	Duloxetine	Depression	Stress urinary Incontinence	66
74	Ebastine	Anti-inflammatory/Immunomodulatory	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
75	Ebselen	Bipolar disorder	Antimicrobial	45
76	Edaravone	Neuroprotective agent	Multiple sclerosis	34
77	Eltrombopag	Anti-inflammatory	Active against fungal	40

			biofilm	
78	Erythromycin	Antibiotic	Invasive mycosis	67
79	Esketamine (S enantiomer of ketamine)	Intravenous anesthetic	Treatment-resistant major depressive disorder (TRD)	68
80	Etodolac	Anti-inflammatory	Fungal biofilm-targeting	69
81	Etomoxir	Chronic heart failure, Diabetes mellitus	Bladder cancer (under pre-clinical trials)	69
82	Ethinyl estradiol	Turner syndrome	MI, memory disorder	30
83	Everolimus	Breast adeno carcinoma	Renal cell carcinoma	30
84	Exemestane	Ovulation induction	Breast carcinoma	38
85	Exenatide	Type 2 Diabetes mellitus	Acute coronary syndrome	70
86	Favipiravir	Influenza	Covid 19	31
87	Fenofibrate	Reduces, triglyceride-rich particles (LDL) in plasma	Reduces macrophage recruitment in abdominal aortic aneurysm	34
88	Filgrastim	Neutropenia	Covid 19	31
89	Finasteride	Benign prostatic hyperplasia	Antimicrobial	45
90	Fingolimod	Transplantation rejection	Multiple sclerosis	71
91	Floxuridine	Colorectal cancer	Antimicrobial	45
92	Fluorouracil	Solid tumors	Breast carcinoma	38
93	Fluorouracil	Solid tumors	Antimicrobial	45
94	Flufenamic acid,	NSAID	Anti-viral	72
95	Fluoxetine	Antipsychotic/Antidepressant, Serotonin selective reuptake inhibitor (SSRI)	Fungal biofilm-targeting, secondary progressive multiple sclerosis (SPMS)	40
96	Fluphenazine	First-generation antipsychotics	Triple-negative Breast carcinoma	34
97	Fluvastatin	Lipid-lowering	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
98	Fulvestrant	Anti-estrogen	Breast carcinoma	38
99	Fusidic acid	Anti-biotic	Anti-viral	72
100	Galantamine	Polio, paralysis	Alzheimer's disease	32

101	Gallium nitrate	Lymphoma and bladder cancer	Antimicrobial	45
102	Gemcitabine	Anti-viral drug	Breast carcinoma	38
103	Genistein	Menopause, osteoporosis, obesity	Prostate cancer, Bladder cancer (under phase III clinical trials)	73
104	Goserelin	Prostate cancer, uterine fibroids, assisted reproduction	Breast carcinoma	38
105	γ -Secretase inhibitors (GSI)	Alzheimer disease: prevent amyloid precursor cleavage	Several inhibitors are being tested against a variety of cancers	34
106	Human Albumin	Blood additive	Immuno-restoration	34
107	Hydroxychloroquine	Antimalarial	Antiviral drug (HIV, Chicken guinea, dengue, SARS-CoV-2)	74
108	Ibudilast	Asthma	Neuropathic pain	75
109	Imipramine	Antipsychotic/Antidepressant	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
110	Iodoquinol	Anti-infective	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
111	Itraconazole	Antifungal	Anticancer	76
112	ibuprofen	Inflammation	Antimicrobial	45
113	Imatinib	Chronic myeloid Leukemia	Gastro intestinal stromal tumors	75
114	Itraconazole	Antifungal	Anticancer	60
115	Ivermectin	Anti- parasitic	Covid 19	31
116	Ketoconazole	Fungal infections	Cushing syndrome	77
117	Ketoprofen	Anti-inflammatory	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
118	Ketorolac	Anti-inflammatory	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
119	Leronlimab	HIV	Covid 19	78
120	Letrozole	Ovulation induction	Breast carcinoma	38
121	Levothyroxine	Hypothyroidism	Chagas disease	79
122	Levothyroxine	Hypothyroidism	Dermatological therapy	80
123	Lopinavir	HIV/ AIDS	Covid 19	31
124	Losartan	Hypertension	Marfan syndrome	81
125	Losartan	Hypertension	Epilepsy	82
126	Lovastatin	HMG Co-A reductase inhibitors	Glioblastoma	41
127	Loxapine	Antipsychotic and	Irritability associated	34

		antischizophrenia	with autism	
128	Lubiprostone	Constipation	Clozapine-induced constipation	83
129	Masitinib	Alzheimer's, multiple sclerosis	Covid 19	31
130	Mebendazole	Antiparasitic/Helminthiasis/Anti infective	Brain cancer (i.e., medulloblastoma and glioblastoma)/Antimicrobial/Fungal biofilm-targeting	40,45,57
131	Meloxicam	Anti-inflammatory/Immunomodulatory	Active against fungal biofilm	40
132	Metformin	Oral hypoglycemic	Prostate cancer, Endometrial carcinoma, Breast carcinoma (under phase IV clinical trials)	84
133	Methotrexate	Leukemia	Breast carcinoma	57
134	Mibefradil	Antihypertensive, calcium channel blocker	Short term use as an adjuvant in cancer therapy	34
135	Midazolam	Antipsychotic/Antidepressant	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
136	Mifepristone	Oral contraceptive	Covid 19	31
137	Mycophenolic acid	Immunosuppressant	Anticancer	64
138	Minoxidil	Hypertension	Alopecia	85
139	Molnupiravir	Influenza, encephalitis	Covid 19	31
140	Nelfinavir	Antibiotic	Anticancer	60
141	Niclosamide	Helminthiasis/Anti-infective	Antimicrobial and Fungal biofilm-targeting Treats multidrug-resistant leukemia	40,45,86
142	Nitazoxanide	Antiprotozoal agent	Influenza	34
143	Nitroxoline	Antibiotic	Anticancer	60
144	Nortriptyline	Antipsychotic/Antidepressant	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
145	Oxyclozanide	Helminthiasis	Antimicrobial	45
146	Omarigliptin	Type 2 diabetes mellitus	Neurodegenerative disease	87
147	Orlistat	Obesity	Cancer	75
148	Oseltamivir	Anti influenza	Covid 19	88

149	Paclitaxel	Ovarian cancer, atrial restenosis	Breast carcinoma	38
150	Paliperidone	Schizophrenia	Developmental disabilities	30
151	Pentetic acid	Hypocalcaemia	Antimicrobial	45
152	Perhexiline maleate	Anti-anginal	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
153	Pimozide	Anti-psychotic	Anti-proliferative	89
154	Pioglitazone	Type 2 diabetes mellitus	Lichen planopilaris	90
155	Phenobarbitone	Anticonvulsant	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
156	Promethazine	Anti-inflammatory/ Immunomodulatory	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
157	Propranolol	Beta-blocker	Hemangioma	41
158	Propranolol	Anti-hypertensive	Malignant melanoma (under phase III clinical trials)	91
159	Pyruvium pamoate	Anti-infective	Active against fungal biofilm	40
160	Quinacrine	Helminthiasis	Antimicrobial	45
161	Quinidine	Anti-malarial	Anti arrhythmic	92
162	Raloxifene	Osteoporosis	Breast carcinoma	93
163	Rapamune	Anti-inflammatory/ Immunomodulatory	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
164	Remdesivir	Ebola virus	Covid 19	94
165	Repaglinide	Diabetes mellitus	Prostate cancer, Ovarian cancer (under phase 1 clinical trails)	95
166	Ribavirin	Antiviral drug	Covid 19	96,74
167	Rifampicin	Anti-infective	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
168	Riluzol	Glutamate antagonist	Secondary progressive multiple sclerosis (SPMS)	34
169	Ritonavir	HIV	Kaposi's sarcoma (under phase IV clinical trials)	97
170	Rituximab	Cancer	Rheumatoid arthritis	98
171	Rituximab	Lymphoma	Primary biliary cholangitis	99
172	Rosuvastatin	Hypercholesterolemi	Non-alcoholic fatty liver	100

		a	disease	
173	Saracatinib	Cancer therapy	Mild to moderate Alzheimer disease	34
174	Sarilumab	Rheumatoid arthritis	Covid 19	78
175	Simvastatin	HMG Co-A reductase inhibitors	Glioblastoma	41
176	Sildenafil	Angina	Erectile dysfunction	101
177	Silymarin	Anti-hepatotoxic	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
178	Sirolimus	Immuno suppressant	Lymphoblastic leukemia	102
179	Statins	Hyper-cholesterolaemia	Oncology	34
180	Streptozotocin	Pancreatic islet cell cancer	Antimicrobial	45
181	Sulfadiazine	Anti-infective	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
182	Sulfadimethoxine	Anti-infective	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
183	Sulfamethoxazole	Anti-infective	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
184	Sulfamethoxy-pyridazine	Anti-infective	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
185	Sunitinib	Renal cell carcinoma	Pancreatic neuro-endocrine tumor	32
186	Sunitinib	Renal cell carcinoma	Zika virus	103
187	Tacrolimus	Anti-inflammatory	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
188	Tadalafil	Pulmonary arterial hypertension	Congestive heart failure	104
189	Tamoxifen	Breast carcinoma, Albright syndrome, ovulation induction	Antimicrobial	38
190	Teicoplanin	Antibacterial	Antiviral, potentially repurposable for covid 19 treatment	95
191	Telmisartan	Blood pressure reduction	Abdominal aortic aneurysm	34
192	Temsirolimus	Renal cell carcinoma	Breast adeno carcinoma	30
193	Terbutaline sulphate	Asthma	Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis	102
194	Terlipressin	Hepatorenal syndrome	Shock	30
195	Thalidomide	Morning sickness	Erythema nodosum, multiple myeloma	105
196	Thalidomide	Morning sickness	Leprosy	106
197	Thalidomide	Morning sickness	Neuroinflammation	107

198	Thioridazine	Schizophrenia	Breast carcinoma	89
199	Thiotepa	Immunosuppressant	Breast carcinoma	38
200	Tigecycline	Anti-infective	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
201	Tocilizumeb	Rheumatoid arthritis	Acute coronary syndrome	31
202	Tofacitinib	Rheumatoid arthritis	Myeloma	108
203	Topiramate	Epilepsy	Obesity	109
204	Trametinib	Malignant melanoma with BRAF variant	Lymphatic anomaly and arteriovenous malformation	110
205	Treprostinil	Pulmonary hypertension	Hematopoietic progenitor cell Transplantation	111
206	Toremifene	Infertility with an ovulatory disorder	Breast carcinoma	38
207	Umifenavir	Influenza and other respiratory virus	Covid 19	31
208	Valproic acid	Seizures	Bipolar disorder	30
209	Verapamil	Calcium channel blockers	Colorectal cancer	41
210	Valsartan	hypertension	Alzheimer's disease	75
211	Vinblastine	Hodgkin lymphoma, non-Hod gkin's lymphoma, histiocytosis	Breast carcinoma	38
212	Yohimbine hydrochloride	Vasodilator	Fungal biofilm-targeting	40
213	Zidovudine	Cancer	HIV/ AIDS	112
214	Zolmitriptan	Migraine	Cocaine use disorder	113

6. Limitations: To find out the new therapeutic use for the existing drug is a difficult task. Identifying a right therapeutic area and perform clinical trials. To decide at which stage of clinical trials or preclinical study to be restarted. If the available clinical data is not satisfying or do not adhere with the guidelines issued by regulatory bodies one may have to again perform the new preclinical trials and clinical trials. If the repurposed drugs have patents, then it prevents the drugs from entering the market (regulatory constraints). Very weak intellectual property protection is provided for the repurposed drugs and so there are less profits and hence most of the companies do not invest on the drug repurposing. Patents are generally provided for the new chemical entity but not for the new therapeutic use [6]. Lack of interest from

commercial parties and public funding. Barriers to obtain market authorization by academic researchers as they lack the knowledge of authorization process [114].

- 7. Conclusion:** Drug repurposing represents an efficient and effective alternative to traditional drug discovery, addressing the pressing need for treatments in a world facing rapid disease emergence. By repurposing existing drugs, pharmaceutical companies and researchers can bypass many early development stages, thereby reducing costs, accelerating timelines, and increasing the likelihood of success. Various strategies and methods ranging from experimental and *in-silico* techniques to network- and pathway-based methods provide versatile tools for exploring the potential of existing drugs to treat new indications. However, challenges such as regulatory hurdles, intellectual property limitations, and limited patent protection continue to affect the feasibility and profitability of drug repurposing. Overcoming these challenges could further bolster the impact of drug repurposing, providing a critical tool in advancing global healthcare resilience and innovation.
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